

Role of SHG'S In Women Empowerment

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Abstract

Self Help Group is a micro finance setup of 15-20 women and it is a village & urban based financial mediate. SHGs are based on monthly saving and are affiliated to NGOs and Bank. SHGs are under-age and innovative organisational setup in India for welfare and empowerment of women and it

is promoted by Government. SHGs are also best means for providing opportunity to women in order to explore the inner selves and to build their leadership capacity and share ideas with each other. Empowerment is a larger process to enable women to build capacity aimed to greater participation, effective decision making and build greater leadership in them.

This paper will try to find answers to questions like: Are SHGs playing important role in empowering women? What is the role of organisation and what are other different initiatives taken by SHGs to empower women and put them in development of India? The paper will draw experiences from the field work setting.

INTRODUCTION

Self Help Group is a micro finance setup of 15-20 women which can be a village or urban based financial mediate. It is facilitated by NGOs or any self help group promoting institution and is interlinked to bank. It is a volunteering association and is promoted by Government. SHGs also give a platform for women for enhancing their leadership and artistic skills to setup their small-scale industries. These also provide life experiences which eventually enable them to be successful in life.

Self Help Group (SHG) is a process by which is a large group of women (10-20), who come together voluntarily to facilitate savings, credit and income generation to ensure that development activities such as economic freedom. SHG phenomenon certainly instils in women, group consciousness of belongingness, bringing enough

sense of self confidence. In fact, as a person, a woman cannot achieve full and equal dignity in society, their rights as members, roles, privileges and responsibilities of a group with enough understanding about membership. When they become members of SHG they engage in public participation, and social activities. This ensures group-spirit, increased self-esteem and fulfilment in life. Such participation expands horizons of participants, evolves them as decision-makers and as democratic, economic, social and cultural beings. In other words, we can say that the SHG, which ultimately contribute to the overall development of a country like India, empower women socially and economically and is an effective instrument. Still a large segment of the population is disadvantaged women, illiterate, exploited both, in the social and economic spectrum, and is deprived of basic rights.

Woman empowerment is a component of 'Mission Convergence' which is run by the Government of Delhi and is implemented through '**Gender Resource Centres**' that are functioning in communities. If SHGs are facilitated by any organization, then these can enable the women of SHGs to access Delhi government's other services through the Samajik Suvidha Kendra which aim towards empowerment of women by intervention in areas like health, literacy, vocational training and livelihood. There are several organisations which take an initiative to train SHG beneficiaries and facilitate them through legal awareness camps and sessions, health camp and OPDs, nutrition camp, sanitation and cleanliness programmes and other activities.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

ROLE OF NABARD THE SHG-BANK LINKAGE AND MICRO FINANCE

S. Selvam, in his book '**Empowerment and Social Development: issues in community participation**' has talked about some aspects of Self-Help Groups and Micro-Finance in India in the 6th Chapter where he has discussed about the SHG-Bank linkage programme led by

NABARD and role. "The SHG-Bank linkage programme led by NABARD in India is considered to be largest and fast growing micro-finance programme in the world in term of its wide outreach. This linkage programme covered over 500 districts in 30 States and union Territories. There are over 2800 NGOs and 3000 branches of 500 banks are associated with micro-credit programme. During the fiscal year ending March 2003, 255, 882 new SHGs were given credit by the banks under the SHG-Bank linkage programme. During this period, banks disbursed Rs. 10,223 million to SHGs. Cumulatively, there are 717, 360 SHGs are now credit linked with different banks. Among these SHGs, over 90% of them have exclusively women members. The increasing volume and spread of SHGs across the country especially in rural India signifies that emergence of hundreds and thousands of local groups for micro-finance related activities. These SHGs are in existence among the poor with some organizational structure and the experience of collective functioning. These are largely used as social collateral structure for micro-finance practices." (Selvam, 2005)

H.Y. Siddiqui, in his book 'Group Work: Theories and Practices' has talked about Self Help Groups in the 11th Chapter where he has discussed about uses of self help groups, objectives of forming such groups, such as

1. For meeting economic needs of the deprived populations
2. For providing psycho- social support to members
3. For dealing with community related problems He has also put forward the stages involved in SHGs. He has ended this chapter with a discussion on case studies on Bangladesh & Pakistan The case study on Bangladesh has been shown below.

"A group of five members is formed with the understanding that each will follow the group norms. Later the monitoring financial institution (MFI) will help them to join a 'Centre' of around five to seven such groups. The MFI checks that all members are poor and

are not related. The members make regular savings with the MFI and also take regular loans. They each have individual savings and loan accounts with the MFI and the main function of the groups and the Centre is to facilitate the financial intermediation process through performing tasks such as:

1. Holding regular and usually weekly centre level meetings supervised by an MFI worker who maintains the records, where savings and repayments are collected and handed over to the MFI worker.
2. Organising contributions to one or a number of group saving funds, which can be used by the group for a number of purposes, usually only with the agreement of the MFI, which maintains the group fund accounts.
3. Guaranteeing loans to their individual members by accepting joint and several liabilities, by raising group emergency funds and by accepting that no members of a group will be able to take a new loan if any members are in arrears.
4. Appraising fellow- members' loan applications, and ensuring that their fellow- members maintain their regular savings contributions and loan repayments.

This effort at introducing a micro finance scheme to rural poor women earned The Nobel Peace prize for the year 2006 for Mohammed Yunus, the founder of the Grameen Bank in Bangladesh." (Siddiqui, 2011)

MAJOR FINDINGS THROUGH CASE STUDIES OF SHGs IN JHARKHAND

Pushpanjali, in her thesis 'Self Help Groups of Women in Jharkhand processes and implications' has talked about Self Help Group in the chapter 5th where she has discussed Case Studies, women managed enterprise in a market, starting a dairy cooperative etc. and she also major finding her studies. Such as

"A number of women have become economically active. And have diversified into different income generating activities and have started contributing to the household well being. One of the critical aspects of the

transformations in the current gendered distributive arrangements is the ownership of assets, as assets can provide women with economic security and also help them leverage access to more productive resources. A number of women, though very few, report increase in control and ownership of resources. As far as control over loans and savings are concerned, FDGs reveal that women generally have this opinion that loans should be used for household well being and it is immaterial whether it is controlled by women. However women do agree that accessibility of loans has influenced the decision making vis-à-vis loans expenditure in favour of women." (Pushpanjali, 2006)

EXPERIENCES FROM THE FIELD

I placed in Prayas Gender resource Centre (GRC) Suvidha Kendra is an initiative by the Department of Women and Child Development, Govt. of Delhi under its Bhagidari Programmes. The GRC is envisaged as an instrument to bring Social, Economic and Legal Empowerment of women, particularly those belonging to the under privileged sections of society. This programme commenced at Bawana J J Colony since April 2007 and Gopalpur/Wazirabad 2009. Centrally under the Prays there are 205 SHGs functioning in the deferent part of Delhi but in the Gopalpur/Wazirabad centre there are 41 Self Help Group running under in the slums and underprivileged community.

Prayas GRC initiate to form SHGs in different localities like Ambedkar Basti, Indira Basti, Wazirabad and Gopalpur to train the women to maintain their register, passbook, etc. properly through the monthly training and leader meetings. The question arises: Why is it important to keep documents like voter ID card, ration card, Adhaar card and other documents properly? In the meeting they get in touch with the governmental scheme and imbibe the importance of leadership. Institution also trains them into income generation programmes. Prayas GRC trains SHGs beneficiaries in making of market base product that is depend on demand like pickle, candle, jam, jute bags, artificial jewelleryes and other income generating goods. Besides the above mentioned engagements, Prayas GRC has also initiated training of women

in saving their money.

Different initiatives to empower women:-

Idea about working of SHGs and the intervention of agencies can be gathered by a close observation of Prayas GRC's programmes undertaken with SHGs.

WASH Programme

Under this programme women of SHGs were taught several things related to health and sanitation; for example, keeping their drinking water clean, safe and pure by using chlorine tablets, washing hands with soap before and after taking food, brushing regularly and so on. Initiatives were also taken under the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan where they cleaned their communities. As a result of this, the women of the SHGs not only learnt personal hygiene but also got enlightened about the benefits of cleaning their locality clean. They were made to understand that a clean locality will ensure better conditions of living and livelihood. If the women begin to take care of themselves properly, they will feel the well being from within which will eventually make them feel empowered. Having felt clean, fresh and healthy, they will be able to invest their energy and resources in productive activities. Thus, it will eventually ensure empowerment of women.

Health Camps

The primary focus of this component is to sensitise women towards their health needs and to promote health seeking behaviour in them by holding regular medical camps in the community. It incorporates reproductive health and menstrual health. This camp has made them aware about the health issues and has provided primary health care services to the vulnerable communities with primary focus on women. However, all these are not done on SHGs only. Women, other than SHG beneficiaries are also engaged. To ensure continuity of the process, the women are enlightened and empowered to such an extent that they can further this process of awareness through peer learning. Along these lines, Mahatma Gandhi had said '**It is health that is real wealth and not pieces of gold and silver**'.

Family Planning

Awareness camps about family planning also ensure that women become aware about advantages of having small family, understanding the value of girl child, availing benefits of governmental schemes by abiding to these parameters, use of contraceptives, giving adequate gap between children, increased age of motherhood and so on. These camps also focus on giving birth to a healthy child. Sessions are taken with women, especially with those in the SHGs. As we know that disempowerment of women has largely been attributed to inherent association of women with motherhood. Therefore, family planning has the element of empowerment of women.

Nutrition Camp

It cannot be denied, as data shows that a large number of women suffer from a number of nutritional deficiencies. Therefore, nutrition camp is a women-centric programme. It is a must target on women of SHGs with a focus on pregnant women, lactating mothers, adolescent girls and elderly women of the communities so that they can avail the benefit of better nutrition. They are also given training to make healthy food. As we all know that healthy women will ensure healthy motherhood and eventually a healthy society.

Legal Awareness Sessions and Camps

Certain values are inculcated in Indian women since their birth that they try to project themselves as 'Sati savitri' and worship their husbands as 'Pati parmeshwar'. As a result of such socialization, women tend to tolerate atrocities silently, without raising their voices. They undergo exploitation at several levels starting from economic disempowerment to marital rape. Legal Awareness Session therefore becomes most important for empowerment of women. These enable women to know about their legal and constitutional rights so that they can protect themselves and fight against domestic violence. They are provided free legal assistance, lawyers and are facilitated in their struggle for rights. Such women are also provided counselling sessions.

Adult Literacy Classes

Adult Literacy Classes are provided to women and especially for SHG beneficiaries to give them basic education so that they can read, understand and deal their own passbooks of SHG account. This type of programme is very important for them and also broke the chain of illiteracy and participating in making India literate. Prayas, in coordination with, NIOS (National Institute of Open Schooling), provide certificate to show them as literates. This programme illuminates them with the light of knowledge which is the basic requirement for empowerment. Illiteracy disempowers people from the core.

CONCLUSION

Experiences of self-help groups in many countries in recent years as an effective strategy and approach has proven to be a great success. Group-oriented efforts in Latin America, Africa and Asia micro credit groups in different countries are examples of the current self-help efforts. Such as micro-credit groups or self-help groups successfully forms are proven, Thailand, Nepal, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka and India in rural groups, the development of local self-help efforts - 10 to 15 members involved in financial activities through cash with Kenya, Tontines occurred Harames or Vietnam or, as in self credit unions, fishermen groups, village-based banks, irrigation groups Indonesia etc, countries self Help Group (SHG) to help efforts through. No doubt, Fundamental Rights, Directive Principles of State Policy and Fundamental Duties etc virtually assure equal status and special protection to women beyond the economic dimension to provide clues for the development of women and equality, autonomy and personal self place emphasis on issues related to dependence. As a group-oriented model, self-help groups in India to improve both individual and collective empowerment through the development of a mechanism for women to get into 'state' and 'status' of women. Domestic violence in India, prices, legal discrimination, rape, child marriage, is mobilized to protest against domestic violence. Thus, it is the power to empower women with different forms of it.

The organizations are played a very important role women empowerment through the Self Help Groups and not only through the SHGs but also

different initiative of organisation helped in empowerment of women. Self Help Groups are only a major platform for women to enhance their participation in the development of the country and it is playing a vibrant role in reducing the poverty levels, generating employment to setup their micro domestic business and empowering women. Various studies have proved that different models of credit linkage programmes are highly successful and the repayment rate is more than 95%. Micro financing or group lending is being looked upon as an instrument that can be considered as the golden stick for development and has become a ladder for uplifting the women they are living underprivileged socially, mentally and attitudinally.

Point of Discussion

- How much do you think SHGs are influential in empowerment of women in India?
- Micro-financing system has been successful in Bangladesh, but has not yet been so much successful in India. What do you think might be the possible reasons?

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Special Courts to deal with cases pertaining to atrocities on SCs/STs

In accordance with Section 14 of the Scheduled Castes and the Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) {PoA} Act, 1989, the State Governments with the concurrence of the Chief Justice of the High Court, specify for each district, a Court of Session to be a Special Court for the purpose of speedy trial of offences under the Act. Accordingly, State Governments of Gujarat, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh and Rajasthan have designated District Session Courts as Special Courts. Further, to accelerate the pace of trial of cases under the PoA Act, exclusive Special Courts have also been set up in these States namely Gujarat (26), Maharashtra (3), Madhya Pradesh (43) and Rajasthan (25). The Number of cases disposed off/pending in these Courts are as under:

The data for the year 2015 has not yet been generated by the National Crime Records Bureau.

This information was given by Minister of Law & Justice, Shri D. V. Sadananda Gowda in a written reply in Rajya Sabha on 11 March, 2016.

Report : PIB

Name of State	Year	Disposed off	Pending
Gujarat	2013	1319	10042
	2014	892	7364
Maharashtra	2013	860	8471
	2014	969	7559
Madhya Pradesh	2013	3485	14025
	2014	4111	14268
Rajasthan	2013	1867	14483
	2014	2198	13678